

Human Brain project: ¹

The Human Brain Project (HBP) is building a research infrastructure to help advance neuroscience, medicine, and computing. Made to deepen understanding of human brain structure and function, by building a European research infrastructure that harnesses multiple disciplines and computing, and advances science, ICT and medicine, to the benefit of society.

Positive remarks:

The website is full of well categorised information, easy to browse. The research is interdisciplinary and contains a lot of publications accessible to anyone. You can find, share and use data and the project encourages collaboration.

Event Horizon Telescope: ²

The Event Horizon Telescope is an international collaboration between scientists eager to learn more about black hole physics via VLBI

Positive remarks:

The scientists developing the EHT took the first ever photo of a black hole and through that further confirmed Einstein's theory of space-time and how gravity works. Its continuing to provide an immense amount of information about our universe and the mechanisms behind how it works

Improvements remarks:

The website is highly technical and may benefit from making it a little less technical

Science feedback: ³

Create an Internet where users will have access to scientifically sound and trustworthy information

Positive remarks:

They do an excellent job monitoring or providing feedback to scientific publications in the media

Improvement remarks:

It is not clear how they select the scientific articles to review.

Open Worm: ⁴

A bottom-up project to build the first comprehensive computational model of the *Caenorhabditis elegans* supported by the data from scientific experiments carried out over the past decade

Positive remarks:

All the collaborator and people can share their vision, including scientists, writer, artist, webmaster, philanthropist and curious citizen

Safe cast: ⁵

Safecast is an international volunteer driven non-profit organization who creates useful, accessible and environmental data.

Positive remarks:

Accessible, useful and sharing environmental data at home.

SenseBox.de : ⁶

German start-up introducing non professionals to environmental data measure by providing do-it-yourself connected electronic devices and their softwares

Positive remarks:

- It is accessible to everyone
- It has a lot of informations about how to handle the products on their website
- It is a good introduction to computer science, to environmental research and to data collecting methods
- It is a pluridisciplinary project

Improvement remarks:

- Maybe there could be a multiplayer-device ?
- There is no information about how fragile the devices are, if it breaks easily it should at least be made out of recycled materials
- Maybe there could be a way to get a feed-back from professionals about the experiments ?

Kiron:⁷

Kiron is an NGO specializing in free education for refugees and individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Positive remarks:

Accessible to the disadvantaged. information is easily accessible and digestible.

Improvement remarks:

Google trends suggests that interest has faded dramatically over the past couple years. The could benefit from better marketing campaigns. By only opening to refugees, they are self segregating the population further. In conclusion, its a right step in the wrong direction.

Bibliography:

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